

FLUID DYNAMIC SIMULATION AND EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF HONEYCOMB SEAL STRUCTURES IN ELECTROCHEMICAL DISCHARGE MACHINING

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ABSTRACT

Electrochemical discharge machining (ECDM) is a composite technology that combines electric discharge machining (EDM) with electrochemical machining (ECM). In this study, ECDM was used for the processing of honeycomb seal structures, and fluid dynamic simulation and experimental study were conducted. A vortex effect was observed, hindering the electrolyte flow. Compared to other fluid supply methods, a bilateral fluid supply can reduce vorticity and velocity, weakening the vortex effect. According to the result and the current signals after discrete wavelet transformation (DWT), the higher voltage and flow rate can increase total energy and exacerbate the vortex effect respectively, and strengthen the EDM and ECM effect, resulting in more processing depth, over corrosion depth, and molten product height. However, the higher electrolyte concentration can reduce the EDM effect, and enhance the ECM effect, which leads to more over corrosion depth, less processing depth and molten product height. The research results proved that ECDM has a good effect on processing honeycomb seal structures.

KEYWORDS

Electrochemical discharge machining, Honeycomb seal structure, Surface quality, Energy distribution, Material removal rate

1. INTRODUCTION

A honeycomb seal ring is an advanced sealing device used in aviation engine compressors and turbine rotors. Its structure is a hexagonal honeycomb with a core length of 0.8-1.6mm and a single wall zone width of 0.03-0.05mm [1]. Ni-based high-temperature alloy is the current material used for manufacturing honeycomb seal rings, which have high strength and high temperature resistance. Due to the difficult machining characteristics of Hastelloy X and the special thin-walled structure of the honeycomb seal ring, the traditional contact machining technology has a low material removal rate and can cause problems such as tilting and flanging of the honeycomb cores.

Electrochemical discharge machining (ECDM) is a machining method that combines electric discharge machining (EDM) with electrochemical machining (ECM) to remove materials [3]. It has the characteristics of high efficiency and precision of EDM and high surface quality of ECM [5]. Many scholars have conducted extensive research on the mechanism, technology, and quality. The mechanism of the machining methods related to ECDM is a hot research direction. Tang et al. [8] combined imaging technology with current signals and compared electric

discharge images with corresponding currents. The results showed that the shape of the gas film would change due to the force acting on the gas film, and the electric discharge frequency would also increase with increasing voltage. Shan et al. [9] established an experimental device to induce cavitation bubbles with the assistance of high-speed cameras. It was found that the Joule heat effect can effectively explain the delay of pre-discharge time in low-field strength situations. Zhang et al. [10] studied the mechanism of cathodic electric discharge in electrochemical jet machining under high energy conditions. The results showed that the current density threshold was the main influencing factor, and the shape of the nozzle tip can effectively suppress cathodic electric discharge. Mori et al. [11] directly observed the electric discharge phenomenon using a high-speed camera and found that when the distribution of debris particles was dense, electric discharge in the gap was more likely to occur.

Many researchers have proposed new techniques based on the mechanism research. Surya et al. [12] used copper electrodes and oil as processing materials and designed experiments using the Taguchi orthogonal method to study the effect of graphite powder suspension in an electrolyte medium on material removal rate and surface roughness. Torabi et al. [13] prepared a depth of up to 1000 μm on polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) using ECDM and found that increasing rotational speed would reduce gas film thickness, thereby reducing surface roughness. Zhang et al. [14] added high-concentration electrolytes to short-arc electrochemical machining (SEAM-ECM) and conducted experimental comparisons of different parameters on brass, copper, and graphite electrodes. The results showed that the ECM with DC excitation had higher action intensity and longer arc breaking time, copper had low electrode wear and good surface quality at low electric discharge energy, while graphite had the most outstanding processing potential at high electric discharge energy. Dai et al. [16] studied the removal effect of the resolidified layer on the surface of workpieces in SEAM-ECM. The process of efficiency and quality first were combined to obtain the machined surface without the solidified layer and heat-affected layer. Han et al. [17] proposed a milling process that combines electric discharge ablation machining and electrochemical machining. The results showed that the machining efficiency of this combination milling was enhanced, and the relative tool wear rate was reduced. Yue et al. [19] proposed a rotary sinking electrochemical discharge milling (RSECD) and studied the material removal rate under different parameters. Kung et al. [20] studied the powder-mixed electric discharge machining of cobalt-bonded tungsten carbide (WC-Co), and the results showed that the dispersion of aluminum powder particles resulted in a more uniform distribution of electric discharge energy. Zhang et al. [21] designed a tool electrode based on the Taylor cone theory for electrostatic field induced electrolyte injection, resulting in the electrode lossless. Han et al. [22] used ethylene glycol-based electrolyte in ECDM to obtain a stable gas film and processed narrow slits.

The process parameters can allocate EDM and ECM energy reasonably, thereby improving processing efficiency and quality. Huang et al. [23] conducted electrochemical discharge milling experiments on TC4. The effects of voltage, electrode diameter, feed rate, and rotational speed on side gap and surface roughness were analyzed. Yue et al. [24] found that the current density increased at the bend of the equipotential line, while the electrolyte velocity and maximum feed velocity decreased with the increase of coverage distance. Kiyak et al. [25] studied the effects of electric discharge energy density on material removal rate, electrode wear rate, and surface roughness, and electric discharge energy density was closely related to machining quality. Chen et al. [26] used high-speed rotating tool electrodes and gas-liquid mixed media with a certain pressure to study the electric discharge characteristics of SEAM. The results showed that SEAM has high processing accuracy in air, higher material removal rate during gas-liquid mixing, and hydraulic arc breaking phenomenon occurred in water. Zhao et al. [27] conducted short-arc machining experiments on SKD11, and the results showed that the maximum material removal rate could reach 15745 mm^3/min .

Based on the above research content, it can be found that there are few reports on the material removal of ECDM in thin-walled parts, especially for thin-walled parts with special structures, such as honeycomb seal structures. This study conducted the simulation and experiment on the processing of honeycomb seal structures using ECDM. In the simulation section, three different fluid supply methods were designed to analyze the flow field state. In the experiment section, different variables were used to analyze the evolution process of processing morphology and surface quality. The current signals of ECDM were processed to obtain the characteristics of current signals under different processing states.

2. RESEARCH SECTION

2.1. Material Preparation

The material of the honeycomb seal ring was Hastelloy X, and the honeycomb seal ring was provided by the ANDER TECHNOLOGY Company. Each two cores of the honeycomb seal structure were connected, forming a double wall zone. The unconnected area was the single wall zone. To improve the electric discharge energy density and electrochemical dissolution, while ensuring high-temperature resistance, the tool electrode adopted cylindrical copper tungsten alloy (CuW70), with a diameter of 20mm and a length of 80mm.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of honeycomb seal sample and core

2.2. Simulation Models

The uniformity of flow field distribution in the machining area was related to factors such as fluid supply method and flow channel structure [24]. Based on the complexity of the honeycomb seal structure, three different fluid supply methods were designed, namely front fluid supply in the negative X-axis direction, rear fluid supply in the positive X-axis direction, and bilateral fluid supply on both sides, as shown in Figure 2. The simulation model includes a honeycomb seal structure, the rotating wall of the tool electrode, and the inlet and outlet of the flow field. The outermost walls of the model are outlet, and the XY plane was used to observe the distribution of the flow field. To simplify the simulation model, it was assumed that the machining gap remained 0.05mm throughout the machining process [28].

Figure 2. Simulation models (a) front fluid supply (b) rear fluid supply (c) bilateral fluid supply

When the tool electrode cut into the sample, an arc surface with a shape similar to the cylindrical electrode was formed, as shown in Figure 3. Within the machining gap, five different sampling points were selected based on a distance of 0.025mm from the surface of the tool electrode, as shown in Figure 3 (b).

Figure 3. Cut-in simulation models (a) front fluid supply (b) rear fluid supply (c) bilateral fluid supply

The Fluent module in Workbench19.0 was used for the fluid dynamic simulation. Certain assumptions need to be made about the flow of the electrolyte: (1) The electrolyte was continuous and incompressible. (2) The electrolyte did not contain solids or bubbles. (3) The effect of temperature was negligible. The flow field satisfied $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model [29], the control equation was as follows:

$$\{ \nabla \cdot (\rho u) = 0 \quad \rho(\partial v / \partial t) + \rho(v \cdot \nabla)v = -\nabla P + \nu \Delta v + \rho g \quad (1)$$

Where ρ is the density, v is the velocity vector, P is the pressure, ν is the kinematic viscosity, and g is the gravitational acceleration.

The parameters for fluid dynamic simulation were shown in Table 2. Since the model did not deform, the distribution of electrolytes did not change after one revolution. Therefore, according to the rotational speed, the simulation time was calculated to be 0.12 seconds, and the flow field distribution at this time was observed and analyzed as the simulation results.

Table 2 Fluent parameters

Parameter	Value
Rotation speed (r/min)	500
Machining gap (mm)	0.05
Cutting depth (mm)	1.5
Direction of nozzle	front/rear/bilateral
Total flow rate (L/min)	11
Outlet pressure (MPa)	0
Total simulation time (s)	0.12

2.3. Experimental Equipment and Methods

Figure 4 is a schematic diagram of the experimental device, which can achieve axial movement of X, Y, and Z and rotational movement around the Z axis. The workpiece and tool electrodes were connected to the positive and negative poles of the power supply through power lines. The power supply was powered by a DC power supply (IT6000C, ITECH, China). The current signals were collected by multi-channel data recorders (MR6000, HIOKI, Japan), with a current range of 0 to 2000 A and a collection time interval of 200 kb/s.

Figure 4. Schematic diagram of experimental equipment

In the experimental section, NaNO_3 solution was used as the electrolyte, and the experimental variables included voltage, flow rate, and electrolyte concentration. The experimental parameters were shown in Table 3. Before and after the experimental process, the samples were cleaned for 3 minutes in an ultrasonic cleaning machine equipped with deionized water. In order to accurately measure the processing depth and morphology, an ultrahigh speed and large-scale morphology measurement and analysis system (VR5000, KEYENCE, Japan) was used. Due to the small size of the single core, ultra-depth field scanning microscopes (VHX-6000, KEYENCE, Japan) were used to detect the morphology of the honeycomb core.

Table 3 Experiment parameters

Parameter	Value
Rotation speed (r/min)	500
Initial gap (mm)	0.05
Cutting depth (mm)	1.5
Feed rate (mm/min)	1
Applied voltage (V)	DC, 5, 10, 15, 20
Electrolyte concentration (wt.%)	0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1
Electrolyte temperature (°C)	NaNO_3 , 30
Total flow rate (L/min)	11, 15, 18, 20
Polarity of workpiece	Positive

3. SIMULATION RESULTS AND ANALYSIS OF THE FLOW FIELD

In ECDM, the external fluid supply method can ensure more electrolytes [14], but the flow field distribution should be further clarified. Figure 5 shows the relative total pressure distribution cloud map and pressure change curve.

Figure 5. Pressure cloud map of flow field (a) front fluid supply (b) rear fluid supply (c) bilateral fluid supply (d) curve of pressure change

As shown in Figure 5 (a)-(c), the areas with high pressure were mainly concentrated near the inlet and inside the honeycomb cell. The electrolyte pressure gradually decreased as it approached the machining gap. Besides, the electrolyte pressure on the side without a nozzle supply was much lower than that on the side with a nozzle supply, and the huge pressure difference on both sides was not conducive to the stability of the flow field. In the case of bilateral fluid supply, the pressure was smaller than that of the single fluid supply, but there was a similar pressure change trend on both sides. In Figure 5 (d), the gradient of pressure change corresponding to the sampling point was relatively large by using a single fluid supply. When using a bilateral fluid supply, the pressure changed smoothly, and the pressure value at sampling point C was the lowest. The pressure value gradually increased towards both sides, and the highest pressure value was much smaller than that of a single fluid supply. Figure 6 shows the streamline diagram of electrolyte velocity distribution and the velocity change curve.

Figure 6. Velocity cloud map of the flow field (a) front fluid supply (b) rear fluid supply (c) bilateral fluid supply (d) curve of velocity change

In Figure 6 (a)-(c), the velocity streamlines were parallel laminar flow curves near the inlet, and became disordered near the machining gap and outlet. An obvious vortex effect with rotational streamline can be seen in the simulation results, causing the streamline to become disorganized. From the enlarged view of the honeycomb core, it can be observed that the vortex radius was larger during the front fluid supply, and the entire honeycomb core was filled with vortex. During the rear fluid supply, the vortex was denser. However, during bilateral fluid supply, the vortex effect was weakened. In Figure 6 (d), the change trend of the velocity was similar to the pressure, with higher velocity as it approached the inlet. At point C, the velocity at the bilateral fluid supply was smaller than that of the front or rear fluid supply.

To better understand the vortex effect, it was necessary to analyze the state of fluid motion [30]. The motion equation of electrolyte flow can be expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} \rho \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + \frac{u\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{v\partial u}{\partial y} + \frac{w\partial u}{\partial z} \right) = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial x} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial^2 x} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial^2 y} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial^2 z} \right) \\ \rho \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + \frac{u\partial v}{\partial x} + \frac{v\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{w\partial v}{\partial z} \right) = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial y} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial^2 x} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial^2 y} + \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial^2 z} \right) \\ \rho \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} + \frac{u\partial w}{\partial x} + \frac{v\partial w}{\partial y} + \frac{w\partial w}{\partial z} \right) = -\frac{\partial P}{\partial z} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial^2 x} + \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial^2 y} + \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial^2 z} \right) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Where ρ is density, u , v , and w are the components of the velocity vector, P is the pressure, and ν is the kinematic viscosity.

Vorticity can characterize the rotational properties of fluid flow. Based on the relationship between the formation of the vortex state and velocity field, the rotation equation of electrolyte flow can be obtained:

$$\begin{cases} \left[\frac{\partial w_x}{\partial t} - w_x \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right) - w_y \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) - w_z \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial z} \right) + u \left(\frac{\partial w_x}{\partial x} \right) + v \left(\frac{\partial w_x}{\partial y} \right) + w \left(\frac{\partial w_x}{\partial z} \right) \right] = \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_x}{\partial^2 x} + \frac{\partial^2 w_x}{\partial^2 y} + \frac{\partial^2 w_x}{\partial^2 z} \right) \\ \left[\frac{\partial w_y}{\partial t} - w_x \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \right) - w_y \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right) - w_z \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial z} \right) + u \left(\frac{\partial w_y}{\partial x} \right) + v \left(\frac{\partial w_y}{\partial y} \right) + w \left(\frac{\partial w_y}{\partial z} \right) \right] = \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_y}{\partial^2 x} + \frac{\partial^2 w_y}{\partial^2 y} + \frac{\partial^2 w_y}{\partial^2 z} \right) \\ \left[\frac{\partial w_z}{\partial t} - w_x \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right) - w_y \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right) - w_z \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial z} \right) + u \left(\frac{\partial w_z}{\partial x} \right) + v \left(\frac{\partial w_z}{\partial y} \right) + w \left(\frac{\partial w_z}{\partial z} \right) \right] = \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 w_z}{\partial^2 x} + \frac{\partial^2 w_z}{\partial^2 y} + \frac{\partial^2 w_z}{\partial^2 z} \right) \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Where w_x , w_y , w_z are the components of vorticity, u , v , and w are the components of the velocity vector, and ν is the kinematic viscosity.

Vector transformation of the rotation equation can summarize the vorticity equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{w}}{\partial t} - (\mathbf{w} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{w} = \nu \Delta \mathbf{w} \quad (4)$$

Where \mathbf{w} is the vector of vorticity, \mathbf{v} is the vector of velocity, and ν is the kinematic viscosity. Using the Z-axis as the rotation axis, the vorticity size was compared based on the vorticity equation. Figure 7 was the vorticity distribution cloud map.

Figure 7. Vorticity cloud map of the flow field (a) front fluid supply (b) rear fluid supply (c) bilateral fluid supply (d) velocity change of front fluid supply (e) velocity change of rear fluid supply (f) velocity change of bilateral fluid supply

In Figure 7 (a)-(c), high vorticity zones appeared in the area of the tool electrode wall that was near the inlet and within the machining gap. Figure 7 (d)-(f) shows the values of vorticity at different sampling points. For front fluid supply, although there were forward and reverse vorticity zones, the absolute value of vorticity was inversely proportional to the distance from the sampling point to the inlet. The generation of the reverse vorticity zone was due to the counterclockwise rotation of the tool electrode, which hindered the flow of electrolyte in the machining gap, resulting in a vortex effect. Similarly, in the rear fluid supply, the rotation of the tool electrode brought the electrolyte into the machining gap, which was a positive vorticity zone. According to the bilateral fluid supply, the vorticity in the machining gap significantly decreased, and the gradient of vorticity change in the honeycomb core was lower than that of the front or rear fluid supply. This indicates that the flow of electrolytes was relatively stable in the bilateral fluid supply, reducing the problem of rapid changes in electrolyte flow rate.

Through the analysis of the above content, it can be found that there were problems with insufficient liquid supply in some areas, as well as large gradients of velocity and vorticity changes in front and rear fluid supply. Additionally, a large amount of electrolyte can accumulate in the honeycomb core and cannot be circulated with the electrolyte outside the gap, which exacerbates the vortex effect problem. When supplying fluid on both sides, the electrolyte distribution in the flow field area was uniform, and the flow rate was relatively stable. Besides, the vortex effect inside the honeycomb core became weaker. This avoided the problem of insufficient liquid supply on one side, thus ensuring the stability of ECDM.

4. EXPERIMENT RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Cut-Through Morphology Analysis of Honeycomb Seal Structure

According to Section 3, the bilateral fluid supply was selected as the fluid supply method. To study the changes in the processing morphology, different variables of experiments were conducted. When the cutting depth was 1.5mm, fitting curves were performed on the processing morphology, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Cut-through morphology (a) different voltage (b) different electrolyte flow rate (c) different electrolyte concentration

Analyzing Figure 8, the fitted curve had two distinct characteristics, namely the peak curve and the convex curve. When the fitting curve contained more peak curves, the curve became relatively smooth, while there were many convex curves, and the fitting curve became uneven. The reason for this phenomenon was related to double wall and single wall zones in the honeycomb seal structure. During the ECDM, the honeycomb core was subjected to the high-temperature melting effect of EDM and the electrochemical dissolution effect of ECM. Based on Faraday's laws, the materials of single walled zones were removed more than that of double walled zones at the same energy density, resulting in a height difference.

In Figure 8 (a), when the voltage was 5V, the fitting curve had both the peak curve and the convex curve. The possible reason is that when the material removal rate in some processing areas was less than the vertical feed rate of the cylindrical electrode, resulting in contact between the tool electrode and the honeycomb seal structure. The contact behavior had a frictional effect, thus leveling the surface. However, some areas did not make contact and only maintained a small machining gap. The small machining gap leads to stronger EDM and ECM, resulting in a convex curve. However, as the voltage increased from 10 V to 20 V, the fitting curve transformed from the peak curve to the convex curve, indicating that excessive voltage leads to poorer processing morphology.

In Figure 8 (b), the fitting curves transformed from peak curve to convex curve, which means that increasing the electrolyte flow rate made the vortex effect inside the honeycomb cell more obvious, and more electrolytes accumulated inside the honeycomb cell. The areas where electric discharge erosion and electrochemical dissolution occurred also enlarged, making the machining morphology more uneven.

In Figure 8 (c), low electrolyte concentration increased the effect of EDM, and weakened the effect of ECM, resulting in a decrease in the amount of molten products being removed by ECM. Therefore, at low concentrations, the fitting curve showed more convex curves. As the concentration increased, the ECM enhanced, which had a trimming effect on the processed surface, resulting in the peak curve. Figure 9 shows the comparison of processing depth under different variables.

Figure 9. Cut-through depth under different variables and parameters

When increasing the voltage, the energy density in the machining gap was higher, which is conducive to material removal, so the processing depth was also larger. The impact of electrolyte flow rate had a similar impact on the processing depth. When the electrolyte flow rate increased, the processed products were washed away, and ECM acted on the new surface. At the same time, the vortex effect was enhanced, and led to a larger range of ECM inside the honeycomb cell, increasing processing depth. When the concentration of the electrolyte was lower, its conductivity decreased, which made insulation breakdown electric discharge of EDM easier. High electric discharge frequency can accelerate material removal, so the processing depth increases at low concentrations.

4.2. Morphology Analysis of Honeycomb Core

To study the changes in surface morphology, Figure 10-12 shows the detection results of honeycomb cores. Voltage was an important factor that directly affected the surface quality of honeycomb cores. When the voltage was 5V, there were many friction marks on the machined surface, which was related to the wear contact between the tool electrode and the honeycomb seal structure. The phenomenon was consistent with Figure 8 (a). As the voltage increased, molten products appeared on the surface and inside of the honeycomb cell. By comparing Figure 10 (b)-(d), the number and volume of molten products increased. This was because high voltage was more likely to promote electric discharge erosion, causing more materials to melt. At the same time, higher voltage promoted the action of ECM. Based on the vortex effect, ECM continued to occur inside the cores, thereby reducing the thickness of the inner wall of the honeycomb cores. This was not conducive to the practical application of honeycomb seal structures.

Figure 10. Machined surface of honeycomb seal structures at different voltage values (a) 5V (b) 10V (c) 15V (d) 20V

Figure 11. Machined surface of honeycomb seal structures at different flow rates (a) 11L/min (b) 15L/min (c) 18L/min (d) 20L/min

The change in flow rate had an impact on the stability of ECM. In Figure 11, there were always molten products on the surface, indicating that even with an increase in electrolyte flow rate, the molten products cannot be completely washed away. However, the wall of honeycomb core became thinner as the flow rate increased. At high flow rate, the vortex effect was enhanced, resulting in more electrolyte accumulated inside the core. Meanwhile, the range of ECM was enlarged, enhancing the electrochemical dissolution on the inner wall of the core, and forming the thin-walled area.

Figure 12. Machined surface of honeycomb seal structures at electrolyte concentrations (a) 0.4 wt.% (b) 0.6 wt.% (c) 0.8 wt.% (d) 1 wt.%

The concentration of electrolytes affected the degree of interaction between EDM and ECM. By comparing the four electrolyte concentrations in Figure 12, it can be found that at 1%, there was only a small amount of molten products, resulting in relatively good surface quality. However, as the concentration decreased, the number of molten products increased, and the inner wall of the honeycomb core showed a broken wall surface. This was because at low concentrations, the insulation of the electrolyte increased, and the effect of EDM increased. The range and energy density of electric discharge erosion were strengthened, resulting in more broken wall surfaces. The effect of ECM decreased, so the trimming effect on the surface became weaker, resulting in a decrease in the surface quality.

The depth of the depression in the single wall zone was regarded as the over corrosion depth. The comparison of over corrosion depth and the molten product height is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Over corrosion depth and molten product height of machined surface (a) over corrosion depth (b) molten product height

In Figure 13, it can be observed that both voltage and flow rate were positively correlated with the over corrosion depth and molten product height, and concentration was also positively correlated with the over corrosion depth. However, in Figure 13 (b), concentration was negatively correlated with the molten product height. Among the three processing variables, voltage had the greatest impact. Increasing the voltage significantly can increase the total energy, which means that the energy allocated to EDM and ECM also increases.

Increasing the flow rate of electrolytes can also enhance the EDM and ECM. Further electric discharge erosion appeared based on the original molten products, causing the stacking of molten products, and increasing the molten product height. The accumulation of electrolytes inside the core can enhance the vortex effect, and the ECM continued to act on the honeycomb core, resulting in increasing the over corrosion depth.

The concentration of electrolytes mainly affected the conductivity. At low concentrations, EDM had the stronger melting and ablation ability, and the molten product height was the highest. As the concentration increased, the ECM was enhanced, gradually removing the molten products. However, the impact of over corrosion also increased, deepening the over corrosion depth.

4.3. Current Waveform Analysis

The current waveform fluctuated with the processing state being disturbed, resulting in many interference peaks in the current signal waveform. Wavelet transform used a function with fast decay and oscillation as the mother function and obtained the wavelet basis function by scaling and translating the mother function through scaling and translation factors. Due to the variable time-frequency window of the basis function on the time-frequency phase plane, finite signals of different energies can be decomposed according to the basis function, thus meeting the requirements of different resolutions. When the range of the energy signal is limited, discrete wavelet transform (DWT) can be used to process the signal [31], and the expression is as follows:

$$C(a, b) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(t) \frac{1}{\sqrt{a}} \psi\left(\frac{t-b}{a}\right) dt \quad (5)$$

Where $f(t)$ is the initial current signal, a is the scale factor, b is the translation factor, and $\psi(t)$ satisfies the following conditions:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \frac{|\psi(W)|^2}{|W|} dW < \infty \quad (6)$$

DWT can be regarded as a filter that truncates certain frequency components of the signal at different scale factors. Based on the research content of Mallet and Nivin [32], the expressions for high-pass filters and low-pass filters are shown below:

$$\begin{cases} CA_j^d f = \sum_k h(k - 2n) CA_{j+1}^d f \\ CD_j^d f = \sum_k g(k - 2n) CA_{j+1}^d f \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Where h is the low-pass filtering coefficient, and g is the high-pass filtering coefficient.

In order to obtain an approximate coefficient with good discrimination, the basis function was selected as db3 and Level was set as 6. Since the DWT signal was decomposed into half of the previous level signal after each Level, the number of sampling points for the initial signal was 8192, and after 6 decompositions, the number of sampling points was $8192 / 2^6 = 128$.

Figure 14 showed the DWT transformation signals of current signals. When the voltage was 5V, the basis function was db2 and the Level was 6.

Figure 14. Current signal after DWT (a) 5V (b) 10V (c) 15V (d) 20V

In Figure 14, the peak-like EDM current signal and the stable ECM current signal can be observed. The approximate coefficient less than 150 was considered as a weak EDM current signal, while the approximate coefficient greater than 150 was considered as a strong EDM current signal. When the voltage was 5V and 20V, CA6 showed an upward curve. Combined with the analysis of Figures 8 and 10, low voltage leads to friction and high voltage brings high energy density, which leads to the unstable state of the machining process. When the voltage was 10V and 15V, the CA6 curve showed a horizontal fluctuation curve, and there were strong and weak EDM current signals and ECM current signals, indicating that the processing state was relatively stable under these two voltages.

Comparing Figure 14 (b) and (c), it can be observed that at 10V, the EDM current signals were significantly more than at 15V, while the ECM current signal was less. The more EDM current signals represented more electric discharge times, and less energy was allocated to the ECM, resulting in a decrease in ECM current signals.

Figure 15. Current signal after DWT (a) 11L/min (b) 15L/min (c) 18L/min (d) 20L/min

Figure 15 shows the DWT of current signals with different electrolyte flow rates. When the electrolyte flow rate was 11L/min, weak EDM current signals were mainly present on the curve, and the appearance frequency of EDM current signals was relatively low. As the electrolyte flow rate increased, the approximation coefficient increased, resulting in more strong EDM current signal. At the same time, the number of EDM signals also increased. This indicated that under high flow rates, the frequency of electrolyte washing away molten products increased, and electric discharge erosion was more likely to occur on the surface, increasing the electric discharge frequency.

Figure 16. Current signal after DWT (a) 0.4 wt.% (b) 0.6 wt.% (c) 0.8 wt.% (d) 1 wt.%

The current signals of electrolyte concentration were transformed by DWT, as shown in Figure 16. As the concentration of the electrolyte decreased, the approximate coefficient of the strong EDM current signal increased, and the number of weak EDM current signals also increased. While the number of ECM current signals decreased. This was because low concentration reduced the conductivity of the electrolyte, which was more conducive to the breakdown and electric discharge of the insulation medium, resulting in more EDM current signals.

5. CONCLUSIONS

To explore a new technology for processing honeycomb seal structures, ECMD was used in the processing of honeycomb seal structures. Based on the above research content, the main research conclusions were as follows:

1. The pressure distribution of the flow field showed that bilateral fluid supply was more uniform, and the gradient of pressure change was smaller, which can avoid the situation of insufficient supply.

2. The vortex effect observed in the streamline cloud diagram can lead to the accumulation of electrolytes in the machining gap and honeycomb core, which hinders electrolyte flow. When using bilateral fluid supply, the velocity and vorticity distribution on both sides were uniform and smaller, and the vortex effect was weaker.
3. The increase in voltage can increase the total energy, thereby enhancing the interaction strength of EDM and ECM. Similarly, an increase in flow rate strengthened the vortex effect and increased the range of EDM and ECM. Therefore, an increase in voltage and flow rate can increase the processing depth, exacerbating the over corrosion depth and the molten product height. The concentration of electrolytes was negatively correlated with electric discharge intensity and frequency. Increasing the concentration reduced the EDM effect, while enhancing the ECM effect, thereby increasing the processing depth and over corrosion depth, but decreasing the molten product height.
4. After DWT of the current signal, the interference peaks in the original signal can be removed. The results showed that ECDM consists of a strong EDM signal, a weak EDM signal, and an ECM signal. The appearance frequency of the EDM signals was negatively correlated with voltage and concentration, and positively correlated with electrolyte flow rate.

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